

Desalination Approach of Seawater and Brackish Water by Coconut Shell Activated Carbon as a Natural Filter Method

Jayaprakash M C¹, Poorvi Shetty¹, Raju Aedla², D V Reddy³

¹Department of Civil Engineering, Mangalore Institute of Technology and Engineering, BadagaMijar, Moodabidri, Karnataka, India

²GSST, Kumamoto University, Kurokami, Kumamoto, Japan

³Rtd. Professor & Head, NITK, Surathkal; Consulting Faculty, L&T-Ltd-Heavy Civil Infrastructure, Hq- Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

Engineers are challenged to develop cost effective ways to produce large quantities of water suitable for drinking, crop irrigation and commercial use for regions of the world that suffer from water shortages. Water desalination is expensive, requiring large amounts of energy and specialized equipment to convert saltwater into drinking water. The present study aims to develop a cheaper, cleaner, easy and more energy-efficient way of desalinating seawater technique by using natural filters, it can help the common people as it affordable during their immediate requirements. The developed technique seemed to be very effective in reducing the concentration of seawater ions. The desalination system is developed by selecting coconut-shell charcoal as the substrate material. As per the results obtained from prototype of seawater and brackish water, there is 60% reduction in chloride and 75% reduction in sodium; this is mainly due to the usage of activated carbon charcoal as the filter media. It is also observed through experiments that there is 100% reduction in iron, 53% reduction in sulphate, 20% reduction in total dissolved solids and 12% reduction in hardness which clearly indicates that the selected filter medias those are activated carbon charcoal, sand, laterite would be used as the filter medias for future experiments on desalination using natural filters.

This work is to present an overview of current and future technologies applied to the desalination of

brackish as well as seawater to produce freshwater for supplementing drinking water supplies to the common people in smaller quantity. Removal efficiency increases with the increase in contact time respectively, for both seawater and brackish water, which was considered to be maximum purification ~40%.

Keywords: Desalination, Seawater/Brackish water, Activated Carbon, Coconut Charcoal, Eco-friendly.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fresh water today is a scarce resource, and it is being felt the world over. More than 2000 million people would live under conditions of high water stress by the year 2050, according to the UNEP (United Nations Environment Programme), which warns water could prove to be a limiting factor for development in a number of regions in the world. Around one-third of the world population now lives in countries with moderate to high water stress— where water consumption is more than 10% of the renewable fresh water supply, said the GEO (Global Environment Outlook) 2000, the UNEP's millennium report.

As population increase and source of high quality, fresh drinking water decrease, using desalination processes to provide freshwater when other sources and treatment procedures are uneconomical or not environmentally responsible is becoming more and

more common. Desalination is any process that removes excess salts and other minerals from water. In most desalination processes, saltwater (also called “feed water”) is treated and two streams of water are produced: 1. Treated freshwater that has low concentrations of salts and minerals. 2. Concentrate or brine, which has salt and mineral concentrations higher than that of the feed water.

Desalination processes may be used in municipal, industrial, or commercial applications. With improvements in technology, desalination processes are becoming cost-competitive with other methods of producing usable water for our growing needs. The pure water that is obtained after desalination must be re-mineralised to be adequate for human consumption. Desalination has been used for thousands of years - Greek sailors boiled water to evaporate fresh water away from the salt and Romans used clay filters to trap salt. Today’s sophisticated methods still generally use the concepts of distillation or filtration.

Fig.1 Main inputs and outputs in a desalination process

The feed water for desalination processes can be seawater or brackish water. Brackish water contains more salt than fresh water but less than saltwater. Brackish water is commonly found in estuaries, which are the lower courses of rivers where they meet the sea. Two technologies are primarily used around the world for desalination: thermal distillation and membranes. Both technologies need energy to operate and produce freshwater.

Right now, desalinating seawater is the only viable way to provide water to growing populations, and large desalination plants are now a fact of life in Egypt and other Middle Eastern countries. Most of these plants rely on a multi-step process based on reverse osmosis, which requires expensive infrastructure and large amounts of electricity. These plants release large quantities of highly concentrated salt water and other pollutants back into the seas and oceans as part of the desalination process, creating problems for marine environments.

Thus, the present work would make an attempt of using the traditional natural filter media to desalinate the seawater. This approach may help the common people to desalinate sea water on their own in affordable manner.

1.1 Indian Scenario

India has long coast line of nearly 7516.6 km along which several million people live and are engaged in various activities. Availability of fresh water has been the main centre of growth of civilization. However, there is lots of inequality existing on earth, which needs to be artificially corrected through incorporation of technologies. With the growth of world population the need of fresh water has also increased substantially which has resulted in growth of desalination installation as well. Logically the desalination activities are concentrated on those parts of the earth where availability of water is scares. This is precisely the reason why more than 80% of desalination plants are located in the water scares Middle East region. Unequal water distribution also exists within our country and fresh water desalination technology is getting concentrated more on water scares areas. Besides producing desalted water for human consumption and Industrial requirement these technologies are also found to be advantageous in the recovery of water from waste streams. There is no reliable statistics available on number of plants, their capacities, technologies adopted and status on these plants in India. However, rough indications are that there are more than 1000 membrane based desalination plants of various capacities ranging from 20m³/day to 10,000m³/day.

The "best" desalination system should be more than economically reasonable in the study stage. It should work when it is installed and continue to work and deliver suitable amounts of fresh water at the expected quantity, quality, and cost for the life of a project. Engineers are challenged to develop cost effective ways to produce large quantities of water suitable for drinking and crop irrigation for regions of the world that suffer from water shortages. Water desalination is expensive, requiring large amounts of energy and specialized equipment to convert saltwater into drinking water.

2. Objectives

The objective of this work is to present an overview of current and future technologies applied to the desalination of brackish and seawater to produce

freshwater for supplementing drinking water supplies to the common people in smaller quantity.

Desalination of seawater using natural filters can help the common people as it affordable during their immediate requirements.

Race is on to find a cheaper, cleaner and more energy-efficient way of desalinating seawater.

The other objectives include:

- Irrigation (productive use)
- Domestic uses
- Urban and recreational uses
- Aqua culture
- Industrial Chiller
- Fire extinguish

2.1 Inspiration from available natural resources and processes Use of coconut shell charcoal for water purification

Characteristics of coconut shell charcoal

- 100% organic
- Renewable resource
- High Calorific Heat Value
- Environmental Friendly
- Ready available especially in coastal areas

3. Experimental Setup

Preparation of Coconut Shell Charcoal

Burn in open air

50-60 whole shells 1kg of charcoal

Sieve size : 2.36mm – 4.75mm

Through washing; drying

Procurement of other naturally available materials

Fine aggregate: (Sieve size 2.36mm to 4.75mm)

Coarse Aggregate: ~4mm to 10mm

Laterite Pebbles: ~4mm to 10mm

2mm Sand

Laterite ~5mm

4mm Sand

Fig.2 Natural Filter Materials

Coconut Charcoal~5mm

3.1 Charcoal Based Desalination Prototype

Desalination prototype were made using waste PET (polyethylene terephthalate) bottles as a outer cover to prepare the charcoal based prototype in different layers of filter materials. As an approach of preliminary observation FIVE prototypes are made for each seawater and brackish water separately with varying thickness, such that all five prototypes having different layer thickness of activated carbon coconut charcoal along with other natural filter materials to observe the appreciable result.

Sulphate	2830	812	1869	610	35.04	45.53
Total dissolved solids (TSD)	50200	40580	26200	17,480	20	33.28

Table 1: Chemical parameters of feed water after natural filtration

Note: The pressure applied must overcome the natural osmotic pressure. Eg. 600-1200 psi of pressure must be used for seawater, as it has a natural osmotic pressure of 390 psi.

Note: All the data mentioned in the table1 is as per the natural osmotic pressure.

Sea water's conductivity is one million times higher than that of deionized water. High quality deionized water has a conductivity of about 5.5 μ S/m.

4.1 Reduction percentage of desalinated seawater composition

- Reduction in pH: 95.07%
- Conductivity of seawater was out of range.
- Reduction in chloride ion concentration: 28.19%
- Reduction in sodium ion concentration: 95.1%
- Reduction in TDS (total dissolved solids): 20%
- Reduction in Hardness: 8%
- Reduction in Sulphate: 71.30%
- Reduction in iron: 100%

4.1.1 Reduction percentage of desalinated brackish water composition

- Reduction in pH: 92.1%
- Reduction in conductivity: 1.5%
- Reduction in chloride ion concentration: 9.6%
- Reduction in sodium ion concentration: 94.98%
- Reduction in TDS (total dissolved salts): 33.28%
- Reduction in Hardness: 11.42%
- Reduction in Sulphate: 67.36%
- Reduction in iron: 100%

5. Conclusion

The present obtained results will lead to concentrate on the research over desalination process by using locally available natural filters which is a eco-friendly, cost effective technique and can be easily afforded by common people.

As per the results obtained from prototype1 of seawater, there is 60% reduction in chloride and 75% reduction in sodium; this is mainly due to the usage of activated carbon charcoal as the filter media. Better result can be obtained if proper care is taken while conducting the experiments (Coconut shell charcoal might be prepared by heating half splitted coconut shell at a temperature of 900 °C for 4 hours using a muffle furnace for better results).

1. It is also observed through experiments that there is 100% reduction in iron, 53% reduction in sulphate, 20% reduction in total dissolved solids and 12% reduction in hardness which clearly indicates that the selected filter medias those are activated carbon charcoal, sand, laterites can be used as the filter medias for future experiments on desalination using natural filters.
2. As per the results obtained there is 100% reduction in iron, hence it clearly proved that the coconut shell charcoal acts as a purifying agent to remove the iron content.
3. The appreciable result of other composition of feed water such as chloride, sodium, total dissolved solids, sulphate and hardness could not be obtained due to following limitations.

We can overcome those limitations by taking proper care while conducting the experiment and by considering the following points:

Coconut shell charcoal should have been prepared by heating half splitted coconut shell at a temperature of 900 °C for 4 hours using a muffle furnace for better results.

The prototype should be designed in large scale (as it provides large amount of surface area and minimize the rate of filtration in the prototype)

Fig. 4 Bar chart representing the reduction concentration of seawater

Fig. 5 Bar chart representing the reduction concentration of brackish water

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